

Data and Software Availability and Citation Checklist

Use the following checklist to understand what is required and what is considered best practice in following AGU's [Data and Software for Authors](#) Guidance. Refer to the Guidance also for [Availability Statement templates](#) and [Citation examples](#).

Data/Software Availability Statement Elements in Open Research Section:

1. **Description of the Type(s)** of data and/or software - **[Required]**

Examples:

- Data - The facilities of IRIS Data Services were used for access to waveforms and related metadata from the International Geodynamics and Earth Tide Service (Network Of Superconducting Gravimeters, 1997)
- Software - Figures were made with Matplotlib version 3.2.1 (Caswell et al., 2020; Hunter, 2007)

2. **Repository Name(s)** where the data/software are deposited - **[Best Practice]**

Examples:

- [Domain-Discipline Repositories Useful to AGU Journals](#)

3. **URL/link** to the data/software, preferably **Persistent Identifier** (e.g., DOI) and resolves - **[Required]**

Examples:

- Software - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3714460>
- Data - <https://doi.org/10.7283/633E-1497>

If a share link, make sure the link is now a URL/persistent identifier, that it is openly accessible

4. **Access Conditions** - **[Best Practice]**

Examples:

- Registration/fee required
- Database where certain functionality/selections need to be made

5. **English Translation** - **[Required]**

Examples:

- Site includes translation functionality
- Translation available via browser plug-in
- Author guides the readers/makes translation available

6. **Licensing** - **[Best Practice]**

Examples:

- Software - [MIT License](#) ([others](#))
- Data - [CC-BY](#) ([others](#))

7. **In-Text Citation** where possible - **[Best Practice]**

Examples:

- Software - Figures were made with Matplotlib version 3.2.1 (Caswell et al., 2020; Hunter, 2007), available under the Matplotlib license at <https://matplotlib.org/>.

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- Data - Data from the KNMI archive with Federation of Digital Seismograph Networks (FDSN) network identifiers NL (KNMI, 1993) and NA (KNMI, 2006) were used in the creation of this manuscript.
8. If software, also include
1. **Version** (e.g., Version 3.2.1) - **[Best Practice]**
 2. Link to publicly accessible **Development Platform** (e.g., GitHub) - **[Best Practice]**
Examples:
 - Part of the software (version 1.0.0) associated with this manuscript for the calculation and storage of PSDs is licensed under MIT and published on GitHub <https://github.com/Jollyfant/psd-module/> (Jollyfant, 2021).
 3. **Author, Project Name(s)** instead of username(s) (e.g., username123)
 4. **Additional Context/Description** beyond acronym or code name (e.g., Longhorn pipeline scripts for reducing data vs Longhorn)

Data/Software Citation Elements in References Section:

1. Citation in References - [Required]

To support indexing and reuse:

- Use [American Psychological Association \(APA\) style](#)
- Include a persistent identifier (DOI), preferred, or URL
- Use labels/bracketed descriptions are included (e.g., [Dataset], [Software], [Collection], [ComputationalNotebook])

Examples used from:

Koymans, M. R., Domingo Ballesta, J., Ruigrok, E., Sleeman, R., Trani, L., & Evers, L. G. (2021, September). Performance Assessment of Geophysical Instrumentation Through the Automated Analysis of Power Spectral Density Estimates. Earth and Space Science. American Geophysical Union (AGU). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021ea001675>